

Integrated pest management–weeds

Weed control in dry and wet seeded irrigated rice

O. S. Kandasamy and SP. Palaniappan, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003. India

We evaluated 12 weed control treatments involving five herbicides applied preemergence and followed by (fb) hand weeding (HW) and applied early post-emergence in combination with 2,4-D; and two hand weedings during Jun-Sep (kuruvai) and Oct-Feb (thaladi) at Aduthurai. In Jun, dry seeds of TKM9 (110 d duration) were sown on dry field; in Oct, sprouted seeds of IR20 (130 d duration) were sown on a puddled field. The trial was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications.

Soil was clay loam. Preemergence herbicides were applied 5 d after seeding (DAS), early postemergence herbicides were applied 15 DAS. Plots treated with preemergence herbicides were hand weeded at 30 DAS. Plots with two hand weedings were weeded 15 and 30 DAS.

At 60 DAS, weed flora in dry seeded rice consisted of monocots (54%) and

dicots (46%); in wet seeded rice, monocots predominated (79%). Irrespective of season, *Echinochloa colona* was the major grass species; *Cyperus rotundus*, the major sedge. *Ludwigia adscendens* was the major broadleaf. *Marsilea quadrifolia* (a fern) was also important.

In preemergence treatments, thiobencarb (1.0 kg ai/ha) with one hand weeding resulted in the best weed kill and in per-hectare yields of 4.9 t dry seeded rice and 4.6 t wet seeded rice (see table). Butachlor (1.5 kg ai/ha) with one hand weeding, and two hand weedings alone were equally effective. In postemergence treatments, no herbicide was effective in either dry or wet seeded rice. ■

Effect of weed control and seeding method on grain yield and weed weight in direct seeded rice. Aduthurai, India.

Treatment	Rate (kg ai/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)		Weed weight (t/ha)	
		Dry seeded	Wet seeded	Dry seeded	Wet seeded
Unweeded control	-	2.4	2.7	2.4	1.7
Two hand weedings (15 & 30 DAS)	-	4.5	4.6	0.4	0.4
<i>Preemergence</i>					
Thiobencarb fb HW	1.0	4.9	4.6	0.4	0.4
Butachlor fb HW	1.5	4.6	4.5	0.5	0.5
Fluchloralin fb HW	1.0	4.2	4.5	0.5	0.5
Pendimethalin fb HW	1.5	4.2	4.2	0.7	0.5
Piperophos fb HW	1.5	4.0	4.0	0.8	0.6
<i>Early postemergence</i>					
Thiobencarb + 2,4-D	1.0+1.0	3.9	3.8	0.9	0.6
Butachlor + 2,4-D	1.5+1.0	3.6	4.0	0.9	0.6
Fluchloralin + 2,4-D	1.0+1.0	3.5	3.9	0.9	0.7
Pendimethalin + 2,4-D	1.5+1.0	3.5	3.9	0.9	0.7
Piperophos + 2,4-D	1.5+1.0	3.2	3.4	1.0	0.7
LSD (0.05) for all plots, pre-emergence and postemergence		0.1	0.6	0.1	0.1
LSD (0.05) between pre-emergence and postemergence		0.1	0.3	0.1	0.1

Effect of time and number of weedings on direct seeded upland rice yields

J. R. Patel, Indira Gandhi Agricultural University, Sub-Research Centre, Bangoli, Raipur, Madhya Pradesh 493225, India

In Bastar, India, 50% of the cultivable land, more than 40,000 ha, is upland, cultivated primarily by tribal farmers. Mean annual rainfall ranges from 1200 to 1600 mm. Southeast monsoon rains start in June and the rice crop is harvested at the end of the rainy season.

Direct seeding is the preferred rice crop establishment method, and hand weeding is the only method of weed control.

We evaluated eight weed control methods during 1985-86 wet season in a randomized block design with three replications. Widely grown rice variety Culture 1 (90-95 d duration) was used.

Effect of hand weeding on grain yield, straw yield, weed dry weight, and control efficiency in direct seeded rainfed rice at Jagdalpur, Madhya Pradesh, India, 1985-86.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Weed dry weight (t/ha)	Weed control efficiency (%)
No weeding	0.2	0.5	2.8	-
One hand weeding 20 DAS	0.9	1.6	1.2	48.0
One hand weeding 40 DAS	1.2	2.1	1.7	57.3
One hand weeding 60 DAS	0.7	1.5	2.1	40.3
One hand weeding 80 DAS	0.4	1.1	1.0	29.3
Two hand weedings 20 & 40 DAS	1.4	2.4	1.0	64.0
Three hand weedings 20, 40, & 60 DAS	2.0	3.5	0.7	75.3
Four hand weedings 20, 40, 60, & 80 DAS	2.3	3.9	0.3	80.0
LSD (0.05)	0.3	0.5	0.4	-
CV (%)	12.2	10.2	11.8	-

With no weed control, yield was significantly lower (see table). When weeding was delayed, yield decreased proportionately, to the lowest with one weeding 80 d after seeding (DAS). Weeding more than once improved yield

significantly. Straw yield, weed dry weight, and weed control efficiency showed similar trends.

At least two weedings at 20 and 40 d after emergence are needed to protect yield potential. ■